

**Communicating Scientific and Technical Information to Science Educators
in Capas, Tarlac Through the Use of ICTs**

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COMMUNICATING SCIENTIFIC AND TECHNICAL INFORMATION TO SCIENCE EDUCATORS IN CAPAS, TARLAC THROUGH THE USE OF ICTS

Information and communication technology (ICT) is a valuable tool for science communication. It continues to provide channels where scientific communities can interact and exchange information, and disseminate knowledge to the public (Mamon, 2002). On the other hand, ICT also influenced change in science education by improving the teaching and learning experience (Suduc et al., 2011).

Science education is essential in building and strengthening the science culture of a nation. The literacy of people in different fields of science equips them in living in the modern world shaped by advancements in science and technology (Cheng & Shi, 2008). Studying science also molds the minds of learners to make decisions that are objective and fact-based (Ambag, 2019). Despite of the advantages mentioned, teaching the subject can be challenging for educators in the Philippines. Ambag (2019) identified the lack of teachers, laboratories, and quality of resource materials as challenges that the Philippines should work on to improve the way science is taught.

Cheng & Shi (2008) affirmed that the shortage of qualified teachers and the lack of up-to-date and quality curriculum and resource materials in science are global problems. In addition, Strauss et al. (2011) argue that unless teachers participate in the world of science themselves, there will be a gap in teaching science. Both papers point to a solution that can reduce the impact of these barriers, science communication.

Science education and science communication are different domains but their goals overlap. Both want to bring science to the public and to cultivate science culture in the community. To achieve these goals, science communication (scicom) can provide support for science education. Teachers can advance their science literacy through interaction with expert science communicators (Strauss et al., 2011). Scicom brings together scientific expertise and information to support science education and to act as a bridge between scientists and educators (Cheng & Shi, 2008).

The lack of quality resource materials is a persistent problem in Philippine education. In 2018, the Commission on Audit reported that P254-million worth of textbooks including science books being used in public schools contain errors (ABS-CBN News, 2019). Many teachers also pointed out that some of the resource materials they are using are obsolete and error-filled (Ambag, 2019). The lack of transparency in the publishing process and bureaucracy can be traced as the root of this problem (del Mundo, 2015). This scenario can hamper the development of science culture in the country, and it can be a major obstacle in bringing science to the public because of the lack of information during the formative years in school.

Science communication through ICT can facilitate the interaction of scientists, science communicators, and educators to amalgamate expertise and up-to-date information and resources for the enrichment of science education in the Philippines.

Key Audience and Stakeholders

Science educators teaching at the elementary and high school levels are the primary audience of this study. They build the foundation of science literacy in their students by utilizing pedagogical knowledge to help learners appreciate, understand and apply science (Strauss et al., 2011). Science educators in the Philippines are facing the challenge of lack of quality materials (ABS-CBN News, 2019; Ambag, 2019; del Mundo, 2015) and this research aims to utilize science communication with information and communication technologies to reduce the impact of this problem. Because of limitations due to the COVID-19 pandemic, the study will focus on science educators in Capas, Tarlac.

Scientists and science communicators are key stakeholders in reducing the impact of the problem of lack of quality resources. Research produced by scientists can serve as supplementary resource materials for educators. On the other hand, the role of a science communicator is to elucidate the scientific information from the resources to the teachers and to help in transforming the learning approach from a textbook-based approach to inquiry-based approaches (Cheng & Shi, 2008).

Students can be identified as the primary beneficiaries of this research. By addressing the problem of lack of quality resources, students will be exposed to different science literature and knowledge through their teachers.

Objectives

This research aims to:

1. Identify the scientific resources needed by science educators teaching at the elementary and high school levels in Capas, Tarlac.
2. Formulate a science communication strategy using ICT that will deliver the needed resources to the science educators in Capas, Tarlac.
3. Recognize the problems in communicating scientific and technical information using ICT.

SOLUTION SCANNING

This research paper will use the Situational Awareness and Analysis; Solution Scanning; Solution Generation; and Solution Implementation for Sustainable Development (4SforSD) framework. In this section, solutions to efficiently communicate scientific and technical information to science educators using information and communication technologies (ICTs) will be presented. Solution scanning will be used to identify a range of options to solve the problem and present literature that supports these solutions (Sutherland et al., 2014). The specific features and methodologies of the most viable solution will be discussed in the next section.

List of communication strategies using social networking sites

This section will cover interventions that will use social networking sites like Facebook, Twitter and Instagram to convey scientific and technical information to science educators in Capas, Tarlac.

1. Creating a Facebook Page

Facebook pages are already used to share educational resources and to facilitate educational discourse (Walsh, 2011). For example, the Facebook page ‘Free Technology for Teachers’ (<https://www.facebook.com/FreeTech4Teachers>) provides educators tools and resources that they can use to improve their teaching experience. It shows that Facebook Page can be a tool for teachers to gather new ideas and to be updated on new scientific knowledge (Muhtaseb & Battrawi, 2013).

The public presence and reach of a Page (Facebook App, 2010) can help educators gain access to up-to-date knowledge and interact with fellow educators. Different publishing tools like Creator Studio can help in achieving and measuring the success of this goal. In addition, advertising tools like Business Manager can help in creating ads to boost the reach of the content to the target audience.

2. Building a Facebook Group

Facebook Group is a useful tool in building a community. In a study by McClain (2017), Facebook Groups can be considered as science outreach models, and some scientists are their own community managers in the Facebook group they manage. On the other hand, using Facebook Groups is found to be effective in encouraging science discourse among students and teachers (Pai et al., 2017). Different Groups features like Publishing tools, Units, and Watch Party can be useful to communicate information to science educators in Capas, Tarlac.

Groups are designed for a smaller audience to create a space where they can interact and exchange ideas on a common interest (Facebook App, 2010). One advantage of this feature is the community manager and the science communicator can control the privacy of the group and moderate the conversations.

3. Programming a Chatbot on Facebook Messenger

Chatbot on Facebook Messenger is an automated messaging feature that uses artificial intelligence to communicate with users (Hootsuite, 2018). They are used to serve information to users 24/7 and it will be very helpful in transmitting relevant scientific information to educators. The feature is ideal for projects with minimal manpower, and it can also be useful for a large audience that will demand information. According to Smutny & Schreiberova (2020), Facebook Messenger chatbots have been used in the field of education from sending messages to recommending content to users. For this research, a text-based conversational chatbot can be programmed to send scientific information to science educators in Capas, Tarlac.

4. Using Instagram

Instagram is a visual social media platform with the potential to transmit scientific information. This social networking site allows users to share photos and videos with their followers. In an article by Hines & Warring (2019), they narrated that Instagram can be used to share their findings from research, and researchers can answer questions from followers in the comments section. The two scientists concluded that Instagram can amplify the reach of published research to a wider audience.

In addition to photos and videos, Instagram Live can be used to host a Q and A session with scientists and science communicators to create a more interactive experience for science educators. On the other hand, Instagram stories can be a creative way of sharing daily resources for teachers.

5. Using Twitter

Twitter is a social networking platform that focuses on conversations. Scientists are using this social media platform to communicate their research to the public (University of Alberta, 2018; Zuckerman, 2018). Tweets can provide short and easy to digest information for educators, and the threads and hashtags can make locating materials easier.

The Twitter VIT app can also provide Q and A sessions for teachers. In this platform, educators can send questions with the designated hashtags which will be loaded on the app and then, the scientists and science communicators can reply using text or videos to the user (Twitter, 2019).

List of communication strategies using other Internet technologies

This section will cover interventions that will use other Web 2.0 platforms to transmit scientific and technical information to science educators in Capas, Tarlac.

1. Conducting Online Video Conference and Streams

The COVID-19 pandemic halted organizing live events for science communication but new features and technologies like Zoom, Microsoft Teams, and Facebook Live provided virtual venues to host events. Lori McMahan, dean of the University of Alabama Graduate School, stated in an interview that “adapting to science communication by screen,” it removed the location barriers of participants to join the event, and it also encouraged discourse among participants (Windsor 2020). Live Q & A where scientists, science communicators and educators can interact can be conducted in these online video conference and streams programs. For this option, it is important to consider the access of the educators to the Internet and the programs.

2. Creating a Mobile Application

Mobile applications or apps can also be conveyors of scientific knowledge. Creating an app offers new possibilities to deliver information, communicate with the audience and build a community (Scholle, 2015). In a literature review by Zydney & Warner (2016), they have observed four broad categories of apps that can be used for science learning and communication: placed-based data collection tools which record field observation of learners using global positioning system, learning management systems, simulation/games, and productivity tools. Scholle (2015) suggested that an app’s ability to deliver scientific information is dependent on its content, platform availability, user interface, language and features.

3. Sending Email Newsletters

Email newsletters are not just a marketing instrument but it can also be a science communication tool. A newsletter is a material regularly published for people working in the same field (Velasco, 2005). In this research, it is planned to be sent to emails of the target audience to supply them with their needed scientific information, stories and materials. One advantage of sending it through email is that links can be included in the material to provide educators with more science-related resources. In addition, educators can also send requests and questions that can be addressed through email correspondence or in the next issue of the newsletter.

4. Producing Video Content on YouTube

YouTube can serve as a repository of science-related content that the teachers can use. Different educational materials are hosted on YouTube, and the video streaming site has been used by science communicators to upload their content and interact with their audience (Welbourne & Grant, 2015). Science communicators can produce their user-generated content, and upload it to their channel that their audience can access. The manager of the channel can also create playlists that can refer to science-related content from different channels. Livestreaming Q and A sessions with scientists can also be an option in this

platform. The materials that will be produced can also be used by the teachers during their lessons with their students.

5. Writing Blogs

Blogs can create a space for educators to receive scientific information that they can use in their teaching. Despite the existence of social media sites, blogging is still a relevant platform for science communication. In a study by Jarreau & Porter (2017, as cited in Brown & Woolston, 2018), they found out that randomly selected science bloggers received 1,000 views on their posts within a few days. It shows the potential and reach of blogs as tools for science communication. Jarreau (2017) science bloggers should amplify their posts on social media and interact with the audience and other science bloggers to create an impact.

Different ICT platforms can provide support in communicating scientific information with educators in Capas, Tarlac. The ten solutions showed that interaction with the main audience is an essential part of the science communication strategy. Video conference or streams, Twitter and chatbots are platforms with high interaction. Moreover, some interventions can also serve as storehouses of scientific knowledge like Facebook, YouTube, mobile apps, and blogs. On the other hand, newsletters and Twitter can provide a steady stream of science-related resources to teachers. Social media and other Web 2.0 technologies provide new channels for science communication.

However, in choosing the feasible solution, the access of educators to the Internet and the platforms mentioned should be the primary considerations. Despite the shift to online distance learning during this COVID-19 pandemic, Filipino teachers are struggling with their Internet connection to reach their students (Rappler, 2020) and they might have a hard time accessing the mentioned interventions. Hence, building a Facebook Group can be the most viable option. Interactions in a group can happen asynchronously. The Units feature can divide and organize the content for easier reading. Other features like Facebook Live, Q and A and other publishing tools that are available on a Page are also accessible in a Facebook Group but with added security, privacy and conversation moderation. The community manager can also set Group Rules to establish the purpose of the community and prevent conflict among the audience. The details and methodology of this solution will be discussed in the next section.

SOLUTION GENERATION

The ICT channel that this project will utilize is the Facebook social media platform. A Facebook Group will be created to communicate scientific and technical information to science educators in Capas, Tarlac. This community feature of the platform will serve as a repository of scientific information and a place where science discourse can happen. This feature was also chosen because of its community managing and privacy features to facilitate meaningful interactions and protect the privacy of those who will join this project, respectively.

The Audience

Science educators in Capas, Tarlac teaching at the elementary and high school levels are the primary audience of this study. A survey was conducted using Google Forms sent through Facebook Messenger to science teachers of Bueno Integrated School, Capas High School, and Cristo Rey High School on November 09, 2020. The survey which ran for three days was designed to know the scientific information needs of the educators and their capacity to access the platform that will be used for this project. The survey form is available in Appendix A.

When the survey was closed, 15 respondents were able to answer the form. Nine (60%) of the respondents are teaching at the elementary level while six (40%) are secondary school teachers. The age profile of the respondents leans towards the younger demographics with 12 teachers in their 20s and two teachers in their 30s and one educator is 40 years old. The

Figure 1. Age profile of the respondents

teaching experience of the respondents varies with one educator teaching science for three months while the respondent with the longest teaching experience has been handling the subject for 11 years. Despite these variations in age and teaching experience, all of the respondents reported that they have a Facebook account. Majority of the respondents (13) stated that they use Facebook every day and two participants even claimed that they use it three to five times every day.

The respondents were also asked what kind of scientific information they need for their teaching. The options provided in the survey are science experiments, science journalism, science research and an 'Others' option where they can nominate a topic. They were allowed

to choose more than one option. Science experiments garnered 11 votes from the respondents while science research got eight votes. On the other hand, science journalism only got four votes. One respondent said that experiments designed for kindergarten level are also needed and another respondent wishes to get resources about social science.

Based on the information provided by the respondents, science communication using Facebook Groups can be implemented because of the access of the teachers to the platform. The result of the survey will also be the basis for the content plan.

The Channel

The transmission of scientific information to educators will happen within the Facebook Group that will be created by the researcher. The community will be set as a private group and its visibility will be hidden so that only members can find it to protect the information of the educators and to avoid other Facebook users from entering the Group. Invite to the group will happen by sending the link to the participants of the survey and the community manager will handle the approval of the members. In addition, the group type will be 'Social Learning' to divide the content into Units that the member can see. This feature will also allow the participants of the research to monitor posts they have not encountered yet. For the pilot test of this paper, the researcher will serve as the administrator, moderator, and publisher for the community.

Facebook Groups offer features that can enrich this project. Publishing of content divided into units can be posted on the group. Units allow members to check their progress on the content. Scientists can also be invited to interact with educators through Live Q and A. The publisher of the Group can also set Watch Parties of science videos that will be helpful for educators.

Interactions on the group will happen asynchronously except if there will be a Live Q & A. The language that will be used in delivering scientific information through posts will be in English and Filipino. In the comments section, a mix of Filipino and English (Taglish) can be used for a friendlier tone and to create a connection with the audience. If necessary, the researcher can also use Kapampangan as a language for interaction.

Since it is a Facebook Group, it will not need an allocated budget for boosting and targeting to reach the target audience. But the researcher will need the following resources and budget to implement the project:

- a. Laptop or Smartphone
- b. Internet connection (1299 per month for PLDT 10 Mbps fiber connection)
- c. Access to scientific literature and other resources

The Message and Content

The project will be called 'Siyensiya sa Social Media' (Science in Social Media) to establish that science communication can also happen on platforms like Facebook. The project will be

focusing on providing accurate and up-to-date scientific information to educators and connect them to scientists through their works or even virtually through Q and A sessions.

The project will start as a content provider, and based on the needs assessment survey conducted, the science educators of Capas who participated in the survey stated that their top needs are resources for science experiments and research but we should not also forget that some also voted for science journalism. The content lineup will be divided into themes and these are:

1. **Experiment Time:** This theme will share science experiments to educators that they can use in their classrooms.
2. **Debunking Science Myths:** This theme can cover some errors in modules and textbooks. Posts under this theme can also include research from scientists.
3. **Science Journalism:** This theme can help educators train future science communicators.

The researcher plans to complete the content lineup during the third week of November 2020 and the researcher will also consult educators during the creation of the content plan to ensure that the materials will be relevant for science teachers. The launch of the project will happen on the fourth week of November 2020. The full content plan and the processes will be discussed in Solution Implementation.

SOLUTION IMPLEMENTATION

This section will detail the steps carried out to communicate scientific and technical information to science educators in Capas, Tarlac through the project “Siyensiya sa Social Media.” This part of the paper will also provide documentation as well as the monitoring and evaluation plan for the implementation.

Strategic Design and Development

The Facebook group was created with the specifications mentioned in the preceding section. The group rules were also set upon the creation of the group. These rules will guide the members during their interactions within the group. In addition, the content themes that will serve as the ‘Social Learning Units’ were already created in advance for easier content management.

Figure 2. Group Rules

Figure 3. Social Learning Units

After creating the group, the researcher proceeded to crafting the message and the content of the project. A logo was created to embody the message of the project and to have a consistent design language in all materials. On the other hand, the content plan (See Appendix B) was based on the results of the survey and it is also aligned with the Department of Education’s Most Essential Learning Competencies (n.d.) for science. The materials prepared were set as scheduled posts so the researcher can also focus on facilitating and monitoring interactions of the members.

Figure 4. Logo of the project

Figure 5. Example of scheduled post

Implementation

Teachers of Bueno Integrated School agreed to join the “Siyensiya sa Social Media” Facebook page. The invite was sent through Facebook Messenger and the project was able to gather 12 participants from the school during the pilot run of the project. The scheduled posts did not encounter problems during the implementation and the researcher can monitor how many participants have seen the posts and how many have completed the Units. The researcher organized the posts into Units and grade levels so that the teachers can easily search and refer to the materials when they visit the group.

Figure 6. Organizing the posts by grade level

Figure 7. Organizing the posts into units

Figure 8. Monitoring the completion of Units

The researcher observed low interaction and participation among the participants of the study. One teacher shared that during the implementation of the project the teachers are busy finishing different requirements like modules before the end of the classes on December 12. Because of the asynchronous nature of the interactions in the group, the teachers can go back to the Units that they missed.

Figure 9. Sample post from the group.

Monitoring and Evaluation

Output	Timeline	Indicator	Activity
Identifying the needed scientific information of the audience.	November 9-11, 2020	Top 2 or 3 scientific topics.	Survey among science educators in Capas, Tarlac.
Creating and verifying the content.	November 12-21, 2020	Complete content and communication plan	Content Research Alignment of content with DepEd MELCs
Establishing the Facebook Group	November 21-22, 2020	Create the Facebook Group and check the settings of the Group	Platform Optimization Content scheduling
Growing the audience	November 21-22, 2020	No. of members who joined the project	Send invitation links Monitor analytics
Initiating pilot test of the project	Week 1: November 23-27, 2020	No. of members who joined the project No. of interactions in the project No. of members who finished the Units	Send invitation links Community management Monitor Facebook Group analytics
Continuing the pilot run of the project	Week 2: November 30- December 4, 2020	No. of members who joined the project No. of members who finished the Units No. of interactions in the project	Send invitation links Community management Monitor analytics
Measuring the viability of the project.	Bi-annual survey	No. of members who saw the contents No. of members who finished the Units No. of members who used the content in their classroom	Conduct among science educators in Capas, Tarlac. Check Facebook Group analytics

Table 1. Monitoring and Evaluation Plan

Conclusion and Recommendations

Science communication is not just about the transmission of scientific information to the intended audience. It is also about finding ways how to create an environment for scientific discourse and looking for new channels to store and retrieve information.

The scientific resources needed by science educators like science experiments can be delivered through social media platforms like Facebook. In addition, the feature Facebook Groups also offers ways to store and organize knowledge for easier retrieval.

One hurdle encountered during the implementation of “Siyensiya sa Social Media” is the lack of time of science educators to access the content during the pilot run. The researcher was not able to observe how interactions will play out within the platform. Future studies can do implementation during the vacation months of the school year.

Science communication can provide support for science education. Moreover, information and communication technologies like social media can serve as channels of scientific information. However, additional studies is needed to investigate the interactions of science communicators and educators within social media.

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APPENDIX A

Paghahatid ng Impormasyong Agham at Teknikal sa mga Guro sa Capas, Tarlac Gamit ang ICT (Survey Form)

Layunin ng 'survey' na ito na malaman ang pangangailangan ng mga guro sa Capas, Tarlac sa impormasyong agham at teknikal. Layunin din nito na malaman ang kakayahan ng mga lalahok sa 'survey' na ma-access ang gagamitin na midyum.

* Required

1. Edad *: _____
2. Gaano ka na katagal nagtuturo ng siyensiya o agham? *

3. Sa anong antas ka nagtuturo? *
 - Elementarya
 - Sekundarya
4. Mayroon ka bang Facebook account? *
 - Meron
 - Wala
5. Gaano mo ito kadalas ginagamit? *
 - Tatlo hanggang limang beses kada araw
 - Araw-araw
 - Minsan sa isang linggo
 - Hindi ko ito ginagamit
6. Anong mga paksa sa agham o siyensiya ang nais mo pang mapag-aralan o malaman na makakatulong sa iyong pagtuturo? (Maaaring pumili ng higit sa isa.) *
 - Science experiments
 - Science journalism
 - Science research
 - Iba pa: _____

APPENDIX B

CONTENT PLAN				
WE EK	CONT ENT TYPE	DAY		
		MONDAY Theme: Experiment Time	WEDNESDAY Theme: Debunking Science Myth	FRIDAY Theme: Science Journalism
1	CALL TO ACTI ON	(PHOTO) Anong science experiments ang pwedeng gawin sa patatas?	(PHOTO) Hiwa-hiwalay nga ba ang ‘receptors’ natin ng panlasa? React Like kung OO, Heart kung HINDI.	(POLL) Nakasulat ka na ba ng isang science article? Kung OO, ibahagi sa comments section ang inyong karanasan.
	SCIE NCE INFO	SOURCE: https://sciencing.com/fun-science-experiments-potatoes-8216496.html	SOURCE: https://theconversation.com/that-neat-and-tidy-map-of-tastes-on-the-tongue-you-learned-in-school-is-all-wrong-44217?xid=PS_smithsonian	SOURCE: https://www.upf.edu/pcstacademy/_docs/200706_unesco.pdf

2	CALL TO ACTION	(PHOTO) EXPERIMENT TIME! This week's material is EGG!	(PHOTO) Kulay asul nga ba ang mga 'veins' ng tao? React Like kung OO, Heart kung HINDI.	(VIDEO) How do we write a news story based from a science article?
	SCIENCE INFO	SOURCE: https://gosciencekids.com/dissolving-eggshell-experiment/	SOURCE: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/47812517_Why_do_veins_appear_blue_A_new_look_at_an_old_question	SOURCE: https://www.theguardian.com/science/2014/mar/28/news-story-research-paper-wellcome-trust-science-writing-prize

NOTE: The posts in this content plan were aligned with the Department of Education's K to 12 Most Essential Learning Competencies.

Department of Education. (n.d.). Science. In *Most essential learning competencies* (pp. 376–397). Retrieved November 8, 2020, from <https://commons.deped.gov.ph/K-to-12-MELCS-with-CG-Codes.pdf>

Week 1

- Monday (Theme: Experiment Time)

a. Call to action

CAPTION: Anong science experiments ang pwedeng gawin sa patatas?

PHOTO:

b. Science Information Post

CAPTION:

Sa pamamagitan ng patatas na madalas nating makita sa ating mga kusina, maituturo na natin sa ating mga estudyante ang mga konsepto katulad ng 'osmosis,' 'solutions' at 'chemical energy.' Ang post na ito ay ipapakita ang isang simpleng eksperimento na magtuturo sa mga estudyante ng konsepto ng osmosis. Tignan ang bawat larawan para sa proseso:

Mga kakailanganin:

- 4 na slices ng patatas
- 2 bowls na may tubig
- Asin

Maaring panoorin ang video DITO: https://youtu.be/-Lph_R7jCiI

GRADE LEVEL: Grade 7, 1st Quarter

REFERENCE:

Adams, C. (2017, July 21). *Fun science experiments with potatoes*. Sciencing. <https://sciencing.com/fun-science-experiments-potatoes-8216496.html>

PHOTOS:

[PHOTO CAPTION] Ihanda ang mga gagamitin:
4 na slices ng patatas
2 bowls na may tubig
Asin
(Magpatulong sa mga magulang sa paghahanda nito)

[PHOTO CAPTION] Lagyan ng 2 tablespoons ng asin ang isang bowl.

[PHOTO CAPTION] Lagyan ng tig-dalawang slices ng patatas ang kada bowl.

[PHOTO CAPTION] Maghintay ng 20 minutes

[PHOTO CAPTION] Matapos ang 20 minutes, obserbahan ang kaibahan ng mga patatas mula sa 2 bowls.

[PHOTO CAPTION] Dahil sa paglalagay ng asin sa isang bowl, inalis natin ang tubig sa loob ng patatas kaya ito naging malambot. Ang paggalaw ng tubig mula sa low salt concentration sa high salt concentration ay osmosis.

(Para sa mga guro) Maaari tayong magsagawa ng research sa paggawa ng mga experiments ng mga estudyante. Para sa experiment na ito, maaari nating saliksikin kung nakatulong nga ba ng eksperimento sa pag-intindi ng konsepto ng osmosis.

- Wednesday (Theme: Debunking Science Myth)

a. Call to action

CAPTION: Hiwa-hiwalay nga ba ang ‘receptors’ natin ng panlasa? React Like kung OO, Heart kung HINDI.

PHOTO:

b. Science Information Post

CAPTION: Ang pamilyar na diagram ng mapa ng panlasa ng tao na nakikita natin sa mga aklat at iba pang midya ay matagal ng na-debunk ng mga ‘chemosensory scientists.’ Ang diagram ay hango mula sa malikhaing interpretasyon ng eksperimento ng siyentipikong si David P Hänig at parang ipinakita dito na ang particular na parte ng dila ay responsable para sa isang uri ng lasa. Alam mo ba na ang iba’t ibang ‘receptors’ natin ng panlasa o taste buds ay nakakalat sa ating buong dila?

GRADE LEVEL: Grade 3, 2nd Quarter

REFERENCE:

Munger, S. D. (2015, July 7). *That neat and tidy map of tastes on the tongue you learned in school is all wrong*. The Conversation. https://theconversation.com/that-neat-and-tidy-map-of-tastes-on-the-tongue-you-learned-in-school-is-all-wrong-44217?xid=PS_smithsonian

- Friday (Theme: Science Journalism)

- a. Call to action

CAPTION: Nakasulat ka na ba ng isang science article? Kung OO, ibahagi sa comments section ang inyong karanasan sa pagsulat tungkol sa agham.

POLL OPTIONS: 1. Oo 2. Hindi pa.

- b. Science Information Post

PHOTO:

TEXT: Natatandaan ko noong ako ay nasa elementarya, isa sa mga kinakasabikan na kompetisyon sa paaralan ay ang ‘press conference.’ Naniniwala ako na mahalaga ang papel ng pagsusulat sa paghahatid ng impormasyon sa mga tao. Pero bakit nga ba mahalaga na matuto ang kabataan sa pagsulat ng mga artikulo tungkol sa siyensiya?

Ayon sa UNESCO, ang pag-aaral ng science journalism ay may benepisyo para sa isang bansa: mas nabibigyang atensyon ang mga balita tungkol sa agham, mas darami ang mga taong ‘science-literate’ na maaaring makilahok sa pagresolba ng mga problema ng isang developing country, at ito ay makakatulong sa paggawa ng desisyon ng mga policy-makers (Econnect Communication, 2007). Para sa mga estudyante, maaaring maging daan ang science journalism para tumaas ang interes nila sa agham at maaari silang magkaroon ng karera bilang science communicators. Isa na rin itong pagsasanay para sa kanila sa pagsasaliksik.

Paano nga ba natin maipapasok ang science journalism sa classroom? Ayon kay Black (2018), ang science journalism ay daan para maintindihan ang aplikasyon ng agham sa tunay na mundo. Maaari tayong magpasok ng mga science articles at news clips sa klase sa mga

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diskusyon. Halimbawa, sa talakayan tungkol sa environmental science maaaring mapag-usapan ang tungkol sa pananalasa ng mga malalakas na bagyo sa bansa, ang mga pagbaha sa mga probinsya at ang mga sanhi nito (climate change at deforestation).

Sa iyong palagay, anong mga issue sa ating bansa na may kinalaman sa agham ang maaaring pag-usapan sa inyong klase?

GRADE LEVEL: Grade 9, 3rd Quarter

REFERENCES:

Black, J. (2018, December). *Science Journalism in the High School Classroom*. Carolina.com. <https://www.carolina.com/teacher-resources/Interactive/science-journalism-in-the-high-school-classroom/tr25104.tr>

Econnect Communication. (2007). *Developing a science journalism course for developing countries*. https://www.upf.edu/pcstacademy/_docs/200706_unesco.pdf

Week 2

- Monday (Theme: Experiment Time)

- a. Call to action

CAPTION: EXPERIMENT TIME! This week's material is EGG!

PHOTO:

- b. Science information post

CAPTION: In this experiment, we can show students a stage in the life of a chicken. This activity can be inserted in discussions about how living things reproduce and grow. On the other hand, it can also show how acids and base react with each other (Vinegar is an acid and eggshell that contains calcium carbonate is a base.) For this activity, we will need the following:

- 1 Chicken egg
- White Vinegar
- Clear Jar

Click the album for the instructions.

GRADE LEVEL: Grade 4 2nd quarter

REFERENCE:

Danya. (2015, August 28). *Can you dissolve the eggshell of a raw egg?* Go Science Kids. <https://gosciencekids.com/dissolving-eggshell-experiment/>

[PHOTO CAPTION] Prepare the materials

1. Chicken Egg
2. White Vinegar
3. Clear Jar

[PHOTO CAPTION] Place the egg inside the jar and fill it with white vinegar.

Tell the students to observe the initial reaction of the eggshell with the vinegar.

Let the egg soak in vinegar for a week.

[PHOTO CAPTION] Remove the egg from the jar and wipe or wash off excess eggshell.

[PHOTO CAPTION] The translucent membranes will allow us to observe the yolk.

Remind the students that the final product is not edible.

- Wednesday (Theme: Debunking Science Myth)

a. Call to action

CAPTION: Kulay asul nga ba ang mga ‘veins’ ng tao? React Like kung OO, Heart kung HINDI.

PHOTO:

b. Science information post

Nagmumukha lang na asul ang mga veins sa ating balat dahil sa iba't ibang dahilan. Ayon sa pag-aaral nina Lilge et al. (1996), ang kulay ng ‘blood vessels’ ay naapektuhan ng:

1. Pag-scatter at pag-absorb ng iba't ibang wavelengths ng liwanag ng ating balat
2. Oxygenation ng dugo na nakakaapekto sa pag-absorb ng wavelengths ng liwanag
3. Laki at lalim ng blood vessel
4. Visual perception process

GRADE LEVEL: Grade 6, 2nd Quarter; Grade 9 1st Quarter

REFERENCE:

Lilge, L., Wilson, B., Hibst, R., Steiner, R., Kienle, A., Vitkin, I., & Patterson, M. (1996). Why do veins appear blue? A new look at an old question. *Applied Optics*, 35(7), 1151–1160. <https://doi.org/10.1364/AO.35.001151>

- Friday (Theme: Science Journalism)

- a. Call to action

VIDEO CAPTION: How do we write a news story based from a science article?

VIDEO LINK: https://drive.google.com/file/d/1O6u3tACzBPyJAdW1CwdegZ-_JewR7cUE/view?usp=sharing

- b. Science information post

In this article by Sample (2014) published on ‘The Guardian,’ we will know the basic steps in writing a science article. In my opinion, the most important step is to know our audience. We need to put science information in their context to make it more understandable and usable. We can ask the following questions:

- Who will be our audience?
- What media will we use to deliver the information that is accessible to the audience?
- How will I make my message understandable?
- How will my audience use the information presented?

GRADE LEVEL: Grade 7 1st Quarter

REFERENCE:

Sample, I. (2014, March 28). *How to write a science news story*. The Guardian; The Guardian. <https://www.theguardian.com/science/2014/mar/28/news-story-research-paper-welcome-trust-science-writing-prize>